

CHECKLIST FOR DATA
MANAGEMENT WHEN
WORKING ABROAD

This checklist will help you prepare for carrying out your research data collection in the field, either abroad, or off-site in The Netherlands.

Disclaimer: this guide is not intended to be comprehensive and may not address all circumstances. Check with relevant support staff in your institute to ensure you are not missing anything, especially any legal steps that might be necessary.

0. How to use this checklist

The preparations proposed in this checklist should be made before leaving Leiden. You might consider some as optional.

This symbol indicates steps that will help you to prepare for emergencies. We recommend you have a back-up plan (a “Plan B”) for emergency scenarios.

This symbol indicates suggestions for “What to think about” when planning your procedures or protocols.

Note: if using a printout of this checklist, refer back to the electronic document for links to further information on the web.

Use the [Research Support Portal](#) to find out more about data management at Leiden University.

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1. General preparations

- Perform software updates.
- Install any new tools that are needed, or might be needed, for example, [EduVPN](#).
- Check that you are familiar with all usernames and passwords and know what to do to retrieve passwords.
- Obtain administrative rights to your computer (optional).
- Investigate internet access conditions at your destination and whilst on-route (availability, quality but also security, government policy, and possible restrictions, for example blocked sites or services).
- Remove unnecessary personal or sensitive data from your computer.
- Investigate mobile phone coverage and conditions at your destination.
- Seek out information about the relevant legal framework for your planned activities (for example, personal data collection, intellectual property and copyright, equipment use).
- Check that services you will need will still be available in your time zone (for example, that service updates are not planned during the night at the administration location).
- Purchase necessary electricity adaptor plugs and batteries.
- Check what additional costs you might incur (see what to think about below).

- Check potential weather conditions and prepare your equipment, or take additional equipment, as necessary.

- Carefully investigate what electricity adaptors are needed both for the shape of socket and the input voltage. Note that online information is not always completely accurate.
- Know the time zone difference and check who you can contact and when in cases of emergency.
- Know what you will need to do if your equipment becomes lost or damaged.

Costs to take into consideration

- Protective materials for equipment.
- Replacement hardware.
- Local internet.
- Local mobile phone card.
- Local printing.
- Shipping plus packaging materials.
- Insurance.
- Power adaptors, cables, & batteries.
- Extra external storage drives.

2. Prepare your data storage

- Make an estimate of the size of the data files you will create. An online “free file size calculator” can help to estimate the size of audio or image files.
- Check that you have enough space to store data on your equipment.
- Prepare a system for file-naming (see the handout on this topic on the web pages of the Centre for Digital Scholarship).
- Plan and create a folder structure for organising your data.
- Learn how to encrypt or lock your files if necessary.
- Check how and when back-ups are made, or make your own data back-up protocol (see below).
- Practise your data collection, storage and back-up procedure at home.
- Decide what to do with non-digital data (for example, signed consent forms): will you digitize these, and if so, how and when?

- Make a Plan B for if you produce more data than expected.
- Check you know how to recover data that is accidentally deleted.

Data back-up protocol: make at least one more copy of your data on another storage medium

- **When will you back-up the data you have collected or worked on?** At a certain time of day or after a certain step in your data collection procedure?
- **How secure are the different locations?** It is recommended to use at least one different storage medium for your back-up, for example, if your data is on a physical device, ideally make a back-up in the cloud. Do you need to encrypt the files or add password protection on any storage location? Do you have a safe place to store any physical storage devices?
- **How many back-ups will you make?** When will you have internet access to make a remote back-up? Will you need to synchronize the different versions of files across the different locations? Will you need to delete files from one storage location at a certain point?
- **How will you perform the back-up?** Will you need an internet connection? Will you need to transfer large volumes of data? Do you need cables?

3. Prepare for your data collection

- Prepare and test your equipment.
 - Prepare a codebook in a suitable format (digital, physical, or both) with templates for your fieldnotes, codes, etc. and the (meta)data you will need to collect about your data collection (date, location, etc.)
 - Plan the procedure for what you need and what you will do when you go to collect your data (checklist for carrying out an interview, for example) and for when you have finished the data collection.
 - Make sure you know how to look after your equipment and ensure you have any necessary instruction manuals and spare parts.
 - Prepare any necessary bags and protective materials for carrying equipment safely.
 - Complete the [data processing register](#) in consultation with your faculty Privacy Officer if you are collecting personal data and plan with them a procedure for reducing risks to personal or sensitive data.
 - Prepare any necessary consent forms and have them in a format suitable for using. You can [find examples online](#).
 - Practise your data collection/creation and back-up procedure at home, and also, if possible, in a location that simulates your fieldwork location (away from free wifi, for example).
 - Have a Plan B for data collection if your hardware or software fails for any reason.
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- Plan for any adverse weather conditions.
 - Anticipate any legal problems concerning the permission given to you to collect data.
 - Know what to do if you have a personal data breach (unauthorized access or potential unauthorized access, for example, due to lost equipment).

Securing your data

- Check out the [tips for working securely online](#).
- Check out [what you will need to do if you have a data breach](#).

4. Prepare your data transfer and sharing

- Install any necessary tools for transferring data files from your location to the cloud, for example, SURFdrive or SURFFileSender. See [available tools for sending or sharing files](#) for Leiden University staff.
- Find out where you will be able to get secure internet access if you need to transfer personal or sensitive data.
- Check with your research partners when and how they would like access to your data.
- Check with your local collaborators whether they would like access to data or results and think about how to deliver these. It might be easier to transfer data to them whilst you are there rather than wait until you are back in Leiden. Think about how long this might take and whether you will need to carry out any training for them.
- Avoid sharing data with those who should not have access by checking the university's guidelines on [working securely online](#).

Plan your time effectively

- **Plan to organise your data and files.** Estimate and plan for the amount of time you will need to manage your data whilst you are away: sorting the data, annotating the files, file naming, backing-up, file transfer or upload, etc.
- **Will you need to process your data before returning?** Don't underestimate the time needed to process your data if you will need to do this on location, for example, to reduce file sizes, make sensitive data more secure, etc.
- **Record details about your data collection as soon as possible.** Create a documentation file about your data as soon as possible so that you don't forget or lose anything: what you have collected, when, from whom, and where. Keep good notes so that you are organized.

If you have any questions there are Data Stewards and other support staff at Leiden University happy to help. Use the [Research Support Portal](#) to find your contact.

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